

VISUALISATION OF THE VACUUM INFUSION PROCESS

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SUMMARY: Three unique ways to visualise the flow processes in vacuum infusion manufacturing of fibre reinforced polymer composites are presented. First, the full 3D position of the flow front is monitored by means of optical measurements, video recording and image analysis. Second, the thickness variation of the reinforcement stack is captured by in-situ measurements of the whole displacement field of the flexible bag using a stereoscopic digital speckle photography system. Third and last, the experimental findings are incorporated in a numerical model, which has been implemented in a general and commercial 3D computational fluid dynamics software. To fully demonstrate the strength of the numerical model it is then applied for simulations of manufacturing of a real detail.

KEYWORDS: Vacuum Infusion, Process Monitoring, Flow Front, Flow Enhancing Layers, CFD

INTRODUCTION

There are numerous ways to manufacture fibre reinforced polymer composites. In fact, the actual number of manufacturing methods and their variants is so large that it would be almost impossible to list them all (Mallick, 1993). However, regardless of the manufacturing method, the flow of resin impregnating the fibres, or in some cases the flow of already impregnated fibres, is in general a very complex process. Furthermore, it is by far the most important factor in determining the quality of the moulded part. It affects everything from fibre distribution and orientation to void content and surface defects. A fundamental understanding of the flow processes is therefore essential in order to ensure optimum and secure processing. Focus of this paper is visualisation of one specific manufacturing method, namely the vacuum infusion process. Spanning over industry scale experiments and advanced numerical simulations, three unique ways to monitor composite manufacturing will be presented.

THE VACUUM INFUSION PROCESS

The basic principle of the vacuum infusion process is that a stack of dry fabrics is placed between a stiff mould half and a flexible and airtight bag. The bag is sealed to the mould except at certain positions being open for resin supplies and outlets. By keeping atmospheric pressure at the resin inlets and reducing the pressure at one or several positions in the formed cavity, liquid resin is forced to impregnate the reinforcement. After complete filling the pressure in the cavity is evened out by retaining the vacuum level at the outlets throughout curing of the resin. The vacuum infusion technique is itself well known and established since long. The first patents are in fact registered already in 1950 (Marco Method). Still, process development has until recent years mainly been based on trial and error and the behaviour of the process is therefore not fully understood and the modelling is so far not sufficient (Williams et al, 1996). The current trend towards increased use of vacuum infusion moulding of larger surface area parts has certainly stressed the risk of a severe economic loss in material value in case of an unsuccessful charge, thus justifying a growing interest for an advanced modelling of the process.

The vacuum infusion process offers an excellent repeatability and is most cost effective for production of large components in smaller series and prototyping (Smith, 1999). General examples of products are hulls to sailing yachts and containers for the transportation industry. As a specific example, the Visby class of stealth corvettes is being built for the Swedish Navy. The closed mould technique implies that negligible amounts of solvents are emitted to the environment. Another advantage, as compared to open methods, is that the fibre content is generally higher and the void content lower, which results in better mechanical properties of the manufactured part. Since the driving pressure in vacuum infusion moulding is unconditionally limited to 1 atmosphere, various flow enhancing methods are often used in order to shorten the cycle-time. This may result in an important out-of-plane flow at the flow-front that is often neglected in the modelling of the well-characterised process resin transfer moulding (RTM). Another difference from RTM is the variation of height of the cavity, primarily due to the difference between the ambient pressure and the resulting pressure gradient within the cavity, but also strongly influenced by lubrication from wetting of the fibres, a time dependent elasticity of the preform and a continuous redistribution of resin.

The main topics to manage are thus: i) the shape and position of the through-thickness flow front, ii) the thickness variation of the stack and iii) a generalisation of the results to form prevalent conclusions valid for arbitrary geometries, material combinations and processing conditions. Based on these specific requirements three unique ways to visualise the flow processes in vacuum infusion manufacturing are presented in the next sections.

OPTICAL MEASUREMENTS OF THE FULL 3D FLOW FRONT

The effect of flow enhancing layers was studied by Sun et al. (1998) by recording of the in-plane flow front position on both sides of a parallel plate tool (for vacuum assisted RTM). In parallel flow under pressure between two stiff mould halves, Diallo et al. (1998) observed both in-plane and through-thickness flow by means of electrically conductive wires inserted in the stack. In our experiments (Andersson et al, 2002) we use a typical vacuum bag infusion set-up with a stiff lower mould half and a flexible and transparent bag on top of 8 layers of a non-crimp stitch bonded reinforcement (ncf) and 1, 2 or 3 layers of a continuous strand mat (csm) used as flow enhancing layers, cf. Figure 1. The monitoring of the through-thickness flow front is based on a most convenient material property, namely that the used reinforcement and flow enhancing layers both become transparent when wetted by the polyester resin. Colour marks are made on every second layer of the ncf, starting with the lowest one. Distributed in the flow direction in sets and within each set slightly sideways displaced not to obscure the view of each other, these marks gradually become detectable as the flow front advances, cf. Figure 1 and Figure 2. Several types of paint were evaluated and the requirements of maximum visibility and minimum disturbance of the flow was finally fulfilled by acrylic touch-up paint (for cars) in different colours. As a further improvement, a 12 mm thick glass plate, with adjustable illumination from below, was used as lower, stiff mould half. The glass plate considerably increased the transparency of the wetted parts of the stack. Video recording of the process also turned out to be most useful in the evaluation phase.

The through-thickness flow front profiles and positions are now derived as functions of time from the measurements of the time when the colour marks become visible from the topline of the stack. As an example, profiles computed at a radial fill length of 240 mm for the cases of 1, 2 and 3 flow layers are shown in Figure 3. Naturally, the three fronts will reach this position at different times since the number of flow layers strongly influence the filling time. The leading dot in each curve of Figure 3 is the flow front position in the uppermost flow layer and the second dot is the position in the uppermost ncf, etc (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic side view of lay-up with three layers of csm on top of eight layers of ncf. Resin flow from left to right. The four colour marks in the wetted region behind the flow front are visible from above, while the four colour marks in the dry region still are invisible.

Figure 2. Through-thickness flow front observations by colour marks in stacking on illuminated glass table. The injection strategy is centralised point injection with radial flow (inlet in the lower left corner). The radial distance between each set of marks is 60 mm. The quarter-circle shaped lines are instantaneous in-plane flow fronts marked with a pen on the bag during injection.

Figure 3. Steady state flow front profiles for 1, 2 and 3 flow layers, derived at a radial distance of 240 mm from the inlet.

DSP MONITORING OF BAG DEFORMATION

The motion of the flexible bag has been observed (Hammami and Gebart, 2000) and measured (Williams et al, 1998) in earlier work. The LVDT-technique used by Williams et al (1998) works well for point wise measurements of the deformation at single positions. It can, however, be more important to continuously measure the deformation of the whole bag as a function of time, in research projects and during production. This is certainly necessarily for process control. The method to measure the movement of the flexible bag presented here is based on an in-house developed stereoscopic digital speckle photography system (DSP) (Andersson et al, 2003(i)). This is an image processing technique, which is field measuring and uses just white light to illuminate the object surface (Sjödahl, 1997). In essence, a random pattern is produced on the surface of the specimen and the motion of this pattern is photographed. By cross-correlating small sub-images of ‘before’ and ‘after’ images of the random pattern, deformation maps can be deduced. To make the system work properly in this context certain actions had to be realized. Several methods to produce and apply dots of the right size (approximately 1 mm^2) on the bag were evaluated. Eventually the final solution was found in two steps. First a foundation layer of matt black spray paint (Alcro Servalac Spray 552) is applied directly on the bag. This layer both eliminates undesired optical reflections and also ensures mechanical adherence to the bag, avoiding any cracking or flaking during processing. After that a top layer of white granite imitation spray paint (Alcro Servalac Spray Granite 581) is applied to generate the actual speckle pattern. Together these two layers provide a fast and operator independent application of appropriate sized speckles with constant optical and mechanical properties, cf. the lower right hand side corner of Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of experimental set-up with speckles applied to the bag.

Two CCD-cameras, each equipped with a 25-mm lens, horizontally separated by 430 mm were mounted 1660 mm vertically above the moulding tool on an aluminium profile purpose-built holding frame. With this set-up, a square area of 250 mm side length was monitored for out-of-plane displacements up to 100 mm with a noise level from the stereo-DSP system itself of less than 10 microns. A full out-of-plane displacement field of the area of observation is exemplified in Figure 5 being the result of an instant measurement 5 minutes after the injection started for an anisotropic ncf lay-up with two layers of csm on top.

Figure 5. Out-of-plane displacement field obtained with stereoscopic DSP system for a vacuum infusion with resin inlet close to the origin and radial resin flow out towards the perimeters.

NUMERICAL VISUALISATION TOOLS

During all fabrication of fibre reinforced polymer composites the resin is, in some way, forced into the fibre network. In order to predict the time for the resin to fill a certain volume of pore space between fibres and the corresponding filling pattern, analytical expressions and mould filling simulation codes have been developed (Diallo et al., 1998; Fracchia and Tucker III, 1990; Gebart et al., 1992; Koorevar, 1995). These tools are mainly designed for the RTM process with stiff moulds and are based on conservation of mass and Darcy's law in 2D. However, due to the flow enhancing layers often used with vacuum infusion moulding, the out-of-plane flow cannot by default safely be neglected. It is thus essential to develop and evaluate new numerical visualisation tools, specifically suited for vacuum infusion. This is rather challenging since the impregnation is characterized by a full three-dimensional flow in a porous medium having an anisotropic, spatial- and time-dependent permeability.

The new approach taken here (Andersson et al, 2003(ii)) is to implement such models in an all-purpose and commercial computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, namely CFX-4 from AEA Technologies, which is a finite-volume based code using a structured multi-block grid (AEA Technology plc., 1999). The advantage of taking such an approach is that the calculations are based on equations tested in numerous applications, that we can do simulation in almost any geometry, and that we, quite easily, can extend our simulations to deal with other constitutive equations and additional phenomena. In essence the following tasks are completed through custom written subroutines in each time step: i) modification of the momentum equations to account for the porous medium flow, ii) coupling of the flow equations to the equations describing the stiffness of the fibre reinforcement, distinguishing between wet and dry response, and iii) remeshing of the computational domain to account for the deformation by the alteration in pressure. The overall strategy has been to first verify and validate the numerical model by 2D simulations (Andersson et al, 2003(ii)) and then demonstrate the full 3D capacity through one demonstrator (Andersson et al, 2003(iii)).

Figure 6. Snapshot of pressure distribution (numbers given in Pa) as obtained with the CFD code for simulation of vacuum infusion. The upper boundary is a flexible bag and the flow is driven from left to right with the highest pressure at the inlet to the left.

Figure 7. Circumferential stiffener used as demonstrator.

Figure 8. Snapshot of pressure distribution approximately half way through filling of the mould as obtained with the CFD code for simulation of vacuum infusion of a real detail (numbers are given in Pa). The inner boundary is a flexible bag, while the outer boundary is a stiff tool. The flow is driven from right to left with the highest pressure at the inlet to the right.

DISCUSSION

It is clear that the development and evaluation of visualisation tools for the vacuum infusion process is essential in order to gain a fundamental understanding of the underlying flow mechanisms. In this paper three unique methods to visualise vacuum infusion manufacturing are presented. Though the actual results from these three measuring techniques fall outside the scope of this paper, they are nevertheless still equally interesting and constitute a base for further amendments on this topic. Future work also involves process optimisation and studies of the effect of new types of materials and processing conditions.

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